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Research Article

ENERGY DRINK CONSUMPTION AND THEIR SLEEP QUALITY EFFECTS IN STUDENTS OF SELECTED COLLEGES OF KALABURAGI DISTRICT” AN EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTIONAL STUDY

¹MD Rehan Shadab, ²Shahid Madhaar, ³Rakkith Bodhi.^{1,2,3} Pharm D intern at, Rajiv Memorial Education Society’s College of Pharmacy, Kalburagi-585102**Abstract:**

Background: Energy drinks (EDs) are non-alcoholic beverages containing high caffeine (>150 mg/L) and sugar; often marketed to enhance energy and performance. However, excessive intake can affect sleep, cognition, and mood.

Aim: To assess the association between energy drink consumption and sleep quality among college students in Kalaburagi city.

OBJECTIVE: To examine the net effects of energy drinks, as well as its potential restorative effects following sleep restriction, performance and mood. To evaluate sleep quality in relation to the consumption of energy drink and other caffeinated beverages among college students. To evaluate energy drink patterns, types of energy drinks commonly consumed, frequency of consumption and motive of participants behind consuming energy drinks.

Methodology: A community-based interventional study was conducted among 457 students aged 16–20 years using a self-prepared questionnaire administered in pre- and post-test phases. Data on consumption patterns, frequency, and types of energy drinks were collected. Sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI).

Results: The mean age of participants was 17.85 years. Males constituted 58% (n=265). Energy drink consumption was reported by 241 (52.7%) students, predominantly males (67.9%). Poor sleep quality was observed in 287 (62.8%) participants. Statistically significant differences were found between energy drink use and poor sleep quality (p<0.001).

Key words: Energy drinks, Non-Alcoholic beverages, Caffeine, PSQI, Interventional

Corresponding author:**Vinod Immanuel,**

Asst. Professor,

at Rajiv Memorial Education Society’s College of Pharmacy,

Kalaburagi-585102

vinodimmanuel@gmail.com

QR CODE

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INTRODUCTION:

Beverages marketed as “Energy Drinks” contain stimulants, particularly caffeine and are marketed as both mental and physical stimulants. They entice the average user by promising increased energy, alertness, and athletic results^[1].

Energy drinks are beverages that typically contain caffeine, taurine, Glucuronolactone, vitamins, herbal extracts, proprietary blends, and physical stamina.[2].

Caffeine has been shown have both positive and negative behavioral, cognitive, and health effects depending on the amount consumed. When consumed in excess, caffeine can Disrupt sleep.[3]. Caffeine, which is an Adenosine receptor antagonist, stimulate the central and peripheral nervous system, affecting the neuronal activities. Taurine which is a sulfur containing amino acid is present as a normal constituent of the human diet. It helps the body to perform physiological functions such as bile acid conjugation, central nervous system modulation, retinal development, endocrinal and metabolic functions, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory functions.[4]

The most common adverse events associated with energy drink Consumption are related to their effects on the cardiovascular and neurological systems followed by gastrointestinal, renal, endocrine, and psychiatric systems.[5]

These adverse effects are related mainly to the consumption of a high amount of Caffeine, which can exceed 500 mg in some EDs, whereas the safe dose is 200 to 300 mg. [6].

Global literature indicates that among students, ED consumption has become a very popular practice due to the marketing claims that EDs can bring about an improvement in mental functioning in the form of increased alertness, improved mood, and enhanced mental and physical energy [7].

An increase in blood pressure and sleep problems has also been reported as a result of high caffeine consumption. Likewise, during pregnancy, it is suspected to raise the risk of late miscarriages, stillbirths and size for gestational age infants. Constantly it is advised to be cautious with the consumption of high levels of caffeine in any form, particularly among health sensitive individuals. [8]

The combination of caffeine and alcohol can reduce the symptomatic fatigue and therefore lead drinkers to fail to guess the level of alcohol intoxication.

This is because the depressant effect of alcohol can mask the stimulant effect of caffeine. [9].

Intake of sugar sweetened beverages also has been

implicated as a likely contributing factor to the growing obesity rates among adolescents because sugared beverages represent a significant source of calorie consumption in this population increasing the risk of non-communicable diseases.[10].

Optimum quantity and good sleep maintain delicate equilibrium between the state of sleep and wakefulness. Poor Sleep quality is linked with poor cognitive performance, poor sleep quality, and emotional dysfunction. The results of bad sleep quality are reflected in next day fatigue and poor concentration. The bad sleep quality contributes to poor academic performance and poor cognitive performance. [11]

Energy drink manufacturers target young adults who are easily lured to consume energy drinks after being exposed to marketing advertisements in the media. An issue of great concern regarding energy drinks is that the information on regarding the negative health effects of excessive intake are not presented over the labels [12].

Insufficient sleep is a major public health concern and a common medical condition with serious adverse consequences. The recommended duration for sleep is 8.5 to 9.5 hours for adolescents (10 to 17 yrs) and 7 - 9 hours for persons who is greater than 18 years of age. Yet many college students do not reach these recommendations and many are sleeping less than 6 hours per night[13].

NEED FOR THE STUDY

This study aimed to investigate the awareness of energy drink consumption and to find out their energy drink pattern, types of energy drink consumed, frequency of energy drink consumed and motive of the participants behind consumption of energy drink among age group of 16 to 20. And the study focuses on investigating sleep quality in relation to the consumption of energy drink and other caffeinated beverages among college students. Hence we chose this study.

AIM AND OBJECTIVES**AIM :**

The aim of the study was to explore Energy drink Consumption is associated with both emotional and behavioral problems and this association is mediated by the amount of sleep disturbances among adolescents.

OBJECTIVES

1) To examine the net effects of energy drinks, as well as its potential restorative effects following sleep restriction, performance and mood.

2) To evaluate sleep quality in relation to the consumption of energy drink and other caffeinated beverages among college students.

3) To evaluate energy drink patterns, types of energy drinks commonly consumed, frequency of consumption and motive of participants behind consuming energy drinks.

4) To examine the relationship between energy drink use, high risk drinking behaviors and other related consequences.

5) To determine if caffeine withdrawal influenced mood and performance by comparing regular consumers who had been withdrawn from caffeine overnight with non-consumers.

METHODOLOGY;

PLAN OF THE STUDY

Duration of Study: Study has been carried out for a period of six months. (March to August)

Study Site: Selected colleges of Kalaburagi, Karnataka.

Study Design: A prospective educational interventional study.

Source of Data: Self structured questionnaires Leaflet has been prepared Literature regarding on Energy drinks

INCLUSION CRITERIA: Students aged between 16 to 20

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

1) Students who are not willing to participate in the study.

2) Students who are taking medications for any illness.

STUDY PROCEDURE

- A prospective community-based intervention study been conducted for a period of 6 months in selected colleges of Kalaburagi city Karnataka after getting approval from IRB (Institutional Review Board)

- All the students meeting the study criteria and agreeing to be a part of study have been given ICF (inform consent form) the ICF that is duly signed by participants are enrolled in the study.

- The information was collected using data collection form

- A baseline score has been taken (pre-test) by interviewing the students using self-prepared questionnaires based on Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) which was used to assess the sleep quality and to research about the impact of energy drink consumption prevalence.

- Then the students were educated by using counseling aids (Information leaflet, videos, PPT...) regarding energy drink consumption and its harmful effects, and its impact on sleep quality among students.

- After the gap of 15 days, we collected the scores for post-test by administering the same questionnaire of pre-test. Finally, the data has been analyzed and interpreted by using proper statistical analysis which is ANOVA

RESULTS:

Table No.1: Distribution of students based on their colleges

Name of the colleges	Number of college students	Percentage
AL-KAREEM	45	9.8
RMES	47	10.3
AL QAMAR	71	15.5
RJ COLLGE	84	18.4
SS TEGNOOR	96	21.0
CHIMALGI	114	25.0
Total	457	100.0

Figure No.1: Bar diagram represents college wise distribution of college students

Table No.2: Distribution of students according to faculty

Course	No. of students	Percentage
D Pharm	23	5.0
GNM	23	5.0
Pharm D	47	10.3
B Sc	70	15.3
PUC	294	64.4
Total	457	100.0

Figure No.2: Bar diagram represents course wise distribution of students

Table No.3: Age wise distribution of students

Age in years	Number of students	Percentage
16	55	12.0
17	188	41.2
18	71	15.5
19	54	11.8
20	89	19.5
Total	457	100.0
Mean \pm SD	17.85 \pm 1.33	

Figure No.3: Simple bar diagram represents age wise distribution of students

Table No.4: Gender wise distribution of college students

Gender	Number of students	Percentage
Males	265	58.0
Females	192	42.0
Total	457	100.0

Figure No.4: Pie chart presents gender wise distribution of students

Table No.5: Pre-test knowledge score of college students

Pre-test knowledge scores	Categories	No. of college students	Percentage
<50%	Poor	231	50.5
50%--75%	Moderately Good	225	49.3
75%--100%	Good	1	0.2
Total	---	457	100.0
Mean \pm SD	3.45 \pm 0.71 (43.1%)		

Figure No.5: Bar diagram represents pre-test knowledge score of college students

Table No.6: Post-test knowledge score of college students

Pre-test knowledge scores	Categories	No. of college students	Percentage
<50%	Poor	0	0.0
50%--75%	Moderately Good	11	2.4
75%--100%	Good	446	97.6
Total	---	457	100.0
Mean \pm SD	7.54 \pm 0.75 (94.2%)		

Figure No.6: Bar diagram represents post-test knowledge score of college students

Table No.7: Comparison of knowledge scores of energy drinks consumption and sleep quality effect between Pre and Post-test

knowledge scores	Categories	Pre-test		Post-test	
		No.	%	No	%
<50%	Poor	231	50.5	0	0.0
50%--75%	Moderately Good	225	49.3	11	2.4
75%--100%	Good	1	0.2	446	97.6
Total	---	457	100.0	457	100.0
Mean \pm SD	----	3.45 \pm 0.71		7.54 \pm 0.75	
Diff. of mean	---	4.05 (94.21%)			
Paired t-test and p-value	t = 92.045, P = 0.0001, HS				

NS= not significant, S=significant, HS=highly significant

Figure No.7: Multiple bar diagram shows the comparison of knowledge scores of energy drinks consumption and sleep quality effect between Pre and Post-test

Table No.8: Pre-test practice of energy drinks consumption and sleep quality among college students

Statements	Options	No. of collage students	Percentage
1. Do you drink energy drinks?	a) Yes	241	52.7
	b) No	216	47.3
2. How often do you consume Energy drinks? (skip if your previous answer was No)	a) At least once a day	81	33.6
	b) At least once a week	106	44.0
	c) At least once a month	54	22.4
	d) I have not consumed yet	216	47.3
3. In what situation do you usually take energy drinks	a) For taste	37	15.4
	b) In need of more energy	68	28.2
	c) While studying for exam	56	23.2
	d) To stay awake	80	33.2
4. Which of the following factors influenced you to take or to continue ED consumption?	a) Friends	50	20.8
	b) Family	11	4.6
	c) Media	90	37.3
	d) self	90	37.3
5. Are you aware of the harmful effects of consuming energy drinks?	a) Yes	323	70.7
	b) No	134	29.3

Table No.9: Post-test practice of energy drinks consumption and sleep quality among college students

Statements	Options	No. of college students	Percentage
1. Do you drink energy drinks?	a) Yes	241	52.7
	b) No	216	47.3
2. How often do you consume Energy drinks? (skip if your previous answer was No)	a) At least once a day	78	32.4
	b) At least once a week	103	42.7
	c) At least once a month	60	24.9
	d) I have not consumed yet	216	47.3
3. In what situation do you usually take energy drinks	a) For taste	38	15.8
	b) In need of more energy	63	26.1
	c) While studying for exam	56	23.2
	d) To stay awake	84	34.9
4. Which of the following factors influenced you to take or to continue ED consumption?	a) Friends	50	20.8
	b) Family	11	4.6
	c) Media	90	37.3
	d) self	90	37.3
5. Are you aware of the harmful effects of consuming energy drinks?	a) Yes	355	77.7
	b) No	102	22.3

Table No.10: Comparison of practice energy drinks consumption and sleep quality among college students between pre and post-test or intervention

Statements	Options	No. of college students		X ² test value P-value & sig
		Pre-Test	Post-Test	
1. Do you drink energy drinks?	a) Yes	241	241	X ² = 0.000 P = 1.000, NS
	b) No	216	216	
2. How often do you consume Energy drinks? (skip if your previous answer was No)	a) At least once a day	81	68	X ² = 0.000 P = 1.000, NS
	b) At least once a week	106	103	
	c) At least once a month	54	55	
	d) I have not consumed yet	216	216	
3. .In what situation do you usually take energy drinks	a) For taste	37	38	X ² = 1.632 P = 0.914, NS
	b) In need of more energy	68	63	
	c) While studying for exam	56	55	
	d) To stay awake	80	84	
4. Which of the following factors influenced you to take or to continue ED consumption?	a) Friends	50	50	X ² = 0.000 P = 1.000, NS
	b) Family	11	11	
	c) Media	90	90	
	d) self	90	90	
5. Are you aware of the harmful effects of consuming energy drinks?	a) Yes	323	355	X ² = 5.849 P = 0.156, S
	b) No	134	102	

Table No.11: Gender wise distribution of energy drinks consumers among college students

Gender	Energy drinks				Total	
	Energy drinks Consumers		Energy drinks non-consumer		consumers	Non-consumers
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Males	167	69.3	98	45.4	265	58.0
Females	74	30.7	118	54.6	192	42.0
Total	241	100.0	216	100.0	457	100.0
X ² test value P-value & sig	X ² = 26.761, P = 0.001, HS					

Figure No.8: Multiple bar diagram represents gender wise distribution of energy drinks consumers among college students

Table No.12: PSQI (Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index) scorings wise distribution of college students

PSQI scorings	Categories	Number of students	Percentage
≤ 5	Good sleep	170	37.2
> 5	Poor sleep	287	62.8
Total	-----	457	100.0

Figure No.9: Pie chart represents PSQI scoring wise distribution of students

Table No.13: Comparison of PSQI scores with energy drinks of college students

PSQI scorings	College students		total
	Energy drink drinkers	Energy drink non-drinkers	
	No (%)	No (%)	
≤ 5 (Good Sleep)	18 (7.5%)	152 (70.4%)	170
> 5 (Poor Sleep)	223 (92.5%)	64 (29.6%)	287
Total	241	216	457
X ² test value P-value significance	X ² = 192.92, P = 0.001,		HS

Figure No.10: Multiple bar diagram represents comparison of PSQI scores with energy drinks of college students

DISCUSSION:

Caffeine is one of the widely used beverages globally as it is a neurostimulator. Caffeine is found in many drinks such as tea, coffee, chocolate, soft drinks, and energy drinks, which are regularly consumed in day-to-day life. Students often reach out for these drinks before a sports event or a long study session as this stimulator gives physical drive for completion of activity. Medical students are at greater risk of dependency of caffeine because of their extensive curriculum which needs to be completed in limited time frame and it requires longer levels of mental and physical functioning.

The study was conducted to identify the relationship between the Energy drink consumption and its sleep quality effects among college students of age 16 to 20. The findings of our investigation can be compared to similar national, regional, and international investigations.

In our study it has been observed that Male students were predominant in the study they were 265 (58.0%) and 192 (42.0%) of students were females and Male to Female ratio was 1.38:1. This was similar to a study conducted by Alfaihi MH et al¹⁵, in which 485(50.3%) were male and 479(49.7%) were females.

In this study, the prevalence of drinkers of energy drinks was 52.7%, among them once a day energy drink drinkers were 33.6%, once week drinkers were 44.0%, once a month drinkers were 22.4%. This has been contrasted in a study by Ayoob Lone et al¹⁶: The intake of caffeine depends on age and, therefore, the main dietary caffeine source varies as age advances. National Health and Nutrition Examination Surveys (NHANES) reported a positive correlation between age and total caffeine consumption until 45–65 years of age. Approximately 70% children and adolescents in the United States consume some form of caffeine on any given day, and around 89% of adults consume caffeinated beverages on a daily basis. The results showed that participants whose age was 19–30 years consumed more coffee than other age groups.

In another study conducted by K Chalachew et al²⁵ mentions that the respondents who used 6–9 cups of daily coffee had four times the odds of having problematic coffee use than those who used <1–3 cups of coffee. Most recent reports European Food Safety Authority suggest that daily caffeine intakes from all sources up to 400mg per day (4 cups) do not raise safety concerns for adults, except for pregnant women.

Majority of students had the influence to drink energy drink were media and self-decision 90 (37.3%) respectively. Situation to take energy drinks were 84 (33.2%) for stay awake, 23.2% for while studying of examination, 28.2% for need of more energy and aware of harmful effects of energy drink in college students was 70.7%.

The current study discovered that out of 457 students, as per Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) scores 287 (62.8%) of students observed poor sleep and 170 (37.2%) of students observed good sleep. The prevalence of poor sleep in college students was 62.8%. These findings were similar to a cross-sectional study by A Ranya et al²⁶ that found poor sleep quality among college students. That could be explained by the need of medical students to study for longer duration at the expense of sleep time.

In our study, we found a non-significant relationship between sleep quality and participant demographics, favourite caffeinated beverages, knowledge-based questionnaire and frequency of energy drink consumption.

The PSQI showed a significant positive correlation. This finding appears to be similar to the findings of another cross-sectional study conducted at the New York College of Podiatric Medicine, which found a link between poor sleep quality and coffee and energy drink consumption. This is not surprising,

given the negative effect of caffeine on sleep structure and circadian rhythm.²⁷

In this study, most of the college students who were taking energy drinks (92.5%) had poor sleep quality, with a non-significant relationship between sleep quality and participant demographics, favorite caffeinated beverage and frequency of energy drink consumption. The PSQI on the other hand, showed a significant positive correlation. Male students had a significantly higher mean frequency of drinking Energy compared to females.

CONCLUSION:

Caffeine consumption was found to be in high prevalence among college students and the average caffeine consumption was found to be higher among males.

The study was conducted on college students belong to the age of 16 to 20, we have enrolled 457 participants in this study. The study focused on giving the awareness of energy drinks consumption and its harmful effects on students' sleep quality and its long-term sleep quality complications.

The overall knowledge and awareness about caffeinated products were found to be low among PU students. Very few students were aware of the harmful effects of energy drinks and the sleep related issues concerning with it.

It is essential to educate young adults about the potential health risks of energy drink consumption and promote healthy lifestyle habits. As the number of adolescents who consume energy drinks is increasing, efforts should be made to provide sleep hygiene education to enable adolescents to better understand sleep hygiene, improve sleep duration and satisfaction, reduce the consumption of energy drinks and to enhance their general well being of the adolescents.

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